

Oncopharmacological aspects of Bcr-Abl inhibitors: from revolutionary structure-based design to clinical resistance

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Abstract

Chronic myeloid leukaemia (CML) represents the first oncological disease in which a direct relationship between a genetic mutation and neoplasia formation has been established. The Philadelphia chromosome leads to the expression of a tyrosine kinase with constitutive activity, providing the basis for the development of targeted pharmacotherapy. The introduction of imatinib marked the beginning of the era of tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKIs) and significantly improved prognosis and long-term survival in CML. Despite these advances, a subset of patients requires treatment modification due to resistance, intolerance, or loss of response, while the need for continuous or lifelong therapy increases the risk of cumulative adverse effects. Together, kinase domain mutations, compound mutations, Bcr-Abl-independent resistance mechanisms, and off-target toxicity expose the practical limits of ATP-competitive inhibition. This review critically examines the evolution of Bcr-Abl inhibitors in light of these constraints and evaluates alternative strategies to achieve more durable disease control.

Keywords

allosteric targeting, drug resistance, proteolysis-targeting chimeras (PROTACs), tyrosine kinase inhibitor

Introduction

The discovery of the Philadelphia chromosome (Ph) is a milestone in the development of oncohaematology, as it was the first to confirm the correlation between a chromosomal aberration and tumorigenesis. This defines chronic myeloid leukaemia as a model disease for the study of the molecular mechanisms of carcinogenesis and for the development of targeted therapy. The reciprocal translocation t(9;22)(q34;q11) results in the formation of the BCR-ABL1 fusion gene, which encodes an oncoprotein with constitutive tyrosine kinase activity and plays a key role in the pathogenesis

of CML (Nowell and Hungerford 1960, 1961; Nowell 1962). The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approval of imatinib in 2001 changed the therapeutic approaches to CML and established the concept of structure-based drug design. In the pivotal IRIS trial, imatinib demonstrated superior cytogenetic and molecular responses compared with interferon-based therapy and significantly reduced the risk of disease progression (O'Brien et al. 2003; Hochhaus et al. 2017). These outcomes established ATP-competitive Bcr-Abl inhibition as the central therapeutic strategy in CML.

Nevertheless, clinical evidence highlights significant limitations, including mutation-driven resistance and the

need for lifelong therapy, which question the long-term effectiveness of ATP-competitive inhibitors. As a result, the therapeutic focus in CML is increasingly shifting from potency-driven optimisation towards strategies that more fundamentally disrupt oncogenic signalling. This review discusses the evolution of these inhibitors and the functional limits of classical kinase inhibition, emphasising the need for alternative disease-control strategies. Loss of sensitivity to allosteric inhibitors and challenges in the clinical translation of proteolysis-targeting chimeras (PROTACs) further demonstrate that no single therapeutic approach can overcome the adaptive capacity of CML cells. Consequently, current research increasingly prioritises the development of multimodal combination therapies.

Materials and methods

This work represents a narrative critical review of the scientific literature on Bcr-Abl tyrosine kinase inhibitors in chronic myeloid leukaemia (CML), with an emphasis on structure-based drug design, mechanisms of resistance, and emerging therapeutic strategies.

Literature search strategy

Relevant publications were identified through searches of PubMed, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. The search included publications from the early development of Bcr-Abl inhibitors to recent advances in the field. Keywords included combinations of “Bcr-Abl”, “chronic myeloid leukaemia”, “tyrosine kinase inhibitors”, “imatinib”, “nilotinib”, “dasatinib”, “ponatinib”, “asciminib”, “resistance mutations”, “T315I”, “allosteric inhibitors”, “combination therapy”, and “PROTAC”.

Inclusion criteria

Priority was given to:

- Peer-reviewed primary research articles;
- Clinical trials and long-term outcome studies in CML;
- Structural biology studies describing Bcr-Abl–inhibitor interactions;
- Mechanistic studies on resistance pathways;
- Recent authoritative reviews and consensus recommendations relevant to CML therapy.

Exclusion criteria

Excluded were:

- Non-peer-reviewed sources;
- Studies not directly related to Bcr-Abl–driven leukaemia;
- Reports lacking sufficient methodological detail or clinical relevance.

This review presents a concept-driven synthesis highlighting the major pharmacological principles, clinical constraints, and future therapeutic directions in Bcr-Abl-targeted therapy.

Results and discussion

Molecular and structural characteristics of Bcr-Abl

The BCR-ABL1 gene results from the fusion of the Abelson tyrosine kinase (Abl1) proto-oncogene on chromosome 9 and the breakpoint cluster region (Bcr) on chromosome 22. The most common transcript isoform in CML is p210^{BCR-ABL} (Lugo et al. 1990; McWhirter and Wang 1993). Different isoforms demonstrate variable sensitivity to tyrosine kinase inhibitors, and their identification is of prognostic importance for therapy. Regardless of the isoform, the primary pathogenetic mechanism in CML is the constitutive tyrosine kinase activity of Bcr-Abl. Effective inhibition of this kinase is the central determinant of therapeutic response, whereas loss of adequate Bcr-Abl suppression contributes to treatment resistance (Melo 1996).

Mechanisms of Bcr-Abl-mediated transformation

Bcr-Abl has complex effects on several fundamental cellular processes, including the regulation of the cell cycle, adhesion, apoptosis, and genomic stability. Protein expression causes a loss of control over cell growth and division. These diverse cellular effects contribute to the persistence of the leukaemic clone despite effective kinase inhibition.

Impaired cell adhesion is an early sign of Bcr-Abl-mediated transformation. Progenitor cells in CML are characterised by reduced adhesion to stromal cells and to components of the extracellular matrix. This leads to increased autonomy of cancer cells (Verfaillie et al. 1997). Inhibition of apoptosis is a central mechanism that supports the survival of Ph-positive cells. The oncogenic protein activates the transcription factor signal transducer and activator of transcription 5 (STAT5), which induces the expression of anti-apoptotic and cell-cycle-regulating genes, including B-cell lymphoma 2 (Bcl-2), B-cell lymphoma-extra large (Bcl-XL), and myeloid cell leukaemia 1 (Mcl-1), as well as Cyclin D1 and c-Myc. The G1/S transition is facilitated, and apoptosis is blocked (Sánchez-García and Grütz 1995; Amarante-Mendes et al. 1998; de Groot et al. 2000; Gesbert and Griffin 2000; Horita et al. 2000; Sillaber et al. 2000; Huang et al. 2002). Bcr-Abl inactivates pro-apoptotic regulators such as Bcl-2-associated death promoter (Bad) and Forkhead box O (FoxO) family transcription factors, thereby inhibiting cytochrome c release and apoptosome formation (Deming et al. 2004; Essafi et al. 2005).

The oncoprotein activates multiple signalling pathways that affect the mitotic potential of leukaemia cells. The rat sarcoma (Ras)/mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK)

cascade is activated via Tyr177-mediated interaction with growth factor receptor-bound protein 2 (Grb2) and son of sevenless (Sos), which stimulates proliferation and cell survival (Campbell et al. 1998; Million and Van Etten 2000). The phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K)/protein kinase B (Akt)/mechanistic target of rapamycin (mTOR) pathway inhibits apoptosis and promotes cell growth by phosphorylating Bad and FoxO (Sattler et al. 1996; del Peso et al. 1997; Franke et al. 1997; Skorski et al. 1997). The increased production of reactive oxygen species leads to the accumulation of DNA damage and an increased frequency of mutations, thereby contributing to the emergence of resistance (Deutsch et al. 2001; Dierov et al. 2004).

Bcr-Abl-mediated signalling alters haematopoietic stem cell behaviour and determines the multi-stage nature of CML pathogenesis. The multiple signalling pathways influenced by Bcr-Abl, along with their synergistic action, define the essential role of tyrosine kinase in disease development (Fig. 1). Bcr-Abl therefore functions as a multifunctional driver of leukaemogenesis, extending well beyond the role of a simple kinase target.

Catalytic domain structure

The catalytic domain of Bcr-Abl has a typical tyrosine kinase bilobal architecture, consisting of N- and C-terminal lobes connected by a hinge region. This organisation forms the ATP-binding pocket. The N-lobe consists of five antiparallel β -sheets and one α -helix (α C) and plays an important role in enzymatic activity. It also contains the ATP-binding loop (P-loop), a glycine-rich region between two β -sheets (β 1 and β 2) in the lobe (Reddy and Aggarwal 2012).

The C-terminal lobe is larger and structurally more complex, includes long α -helices, and contains key structural motifs such as the activation loop (A-loop) and the

catalytic loop (C-loop). The conserved DFG (Asp-Phe-Gly) motif and the regulatory tyrosine residue (Tyr393) are located in the A-loop. The DFG motif is responsible for the coordination of Mg^{2+} ions. Phosphorylation of Tyr393 induces loop extension and unfolding, thereby stabilising the active state (DFG-in). In this conformation, Asp381 of the DFG motif is oriented inward towards the catalytic centre and coordinates the Mg^{2+} ions required for catalysis. On the other hand, in the DFG-out conformation, the DFG motif turns outwards, blocking ATP access and revealing a “specificity pocket” – a small hydrophobic pocket behind Thr315, a target for type II tyrosine kinase inhibitors. The variability of this pocket across different kinases enables the development of selective molecules (Fig. 2) (Shan et al. 2009; Reddy and Aggarwal 2012).

The hinge region connects the N- and C-lobes. It is located between the β 5-sheet of the N-lobe and the first α -helix of the C-lobe (Fig. 3). It maintains the structure of the ATP-binding pocket and interacts with the adenine base of ATP through two hydrogen bonds. This site is a prime target for ATP-competitive tyrosine kinase inhibitors. Thr315 (the gatekeeper residue) is particularly important – it forms hydrogen bonds with several inhibitors, enabling their penetration deep into the hydrophobic pocket. The T315I mutation (replacement of threonine with isoleucine) leads to structural changes at the site: the bulky isoleucine residue causes steric interference, prevents hydrogen bonding, and further stabilises the active conformation (DFG-in) due to its highly hydrophobic nature (Azam et al. 2008; Gibbons et al. 2012). Consequently, T315I has become a paradigmatic case of structure-driven resistance, presenting a major therapeutic challenge (Schindler et al. 2000; Kornev et al. 2006). Understanding the structural architecture of the Bcr-Abl kinase is fundamental for the rational design of targeted therapeutic agents.

Figure 1. Signal transduction pathways involved in Bcr-Abl-mediated cell transformation. Created using ChemDraw v23.0 (demo licence).

Figure 2. Conformational states of the catalytic domain of Bcr-Abl upon binding of tyrosine kinase inhibitors. **A.** DFG-in (active) conformation – Abl kinase in complex with dasatinib (Protein Data Bank (PDB): 2GQG); the activation loop is open, and the DFG motif is oriented towards the catalytic centre; **B.** DFG-out (inactive) conformation – Abl kinase in complex with imatinib (PDB: 2HYY); the activation loop is closed, the DFG motif is turned outward, and an additional specificity pocket is formed behind Thr315, characteristic of type II inhibitors. Structural regions are colour-coded as follows: P-loop (red), α C-helix (forest green), hinge region (cyan), gatekeeper residue Thr315 (yellow), HRD motif (orange), DFG motif (magenta), and activation loop (light blue). The N-lobe and C-lobe are shown in light and dark grey, respectively. Inhibitors are depicted as green sticks. Generated using PyMOL (Schrödinger, LLC; educational licence).

Structure-based design and development of tyrosine kinase inhibitors

Rational design and development of imatinib

Imatinib was developed through structural modification of 2-phenylaminopyrimidine derivatives, which were initially studied as protein kinase C inhibitors (Zimmermann et al. 1997). These modifications aimed to optimise selectivity, potency, and pharmacokinetic properties. Key structural changes include (i) addition of a pyridine ring at the 3'-position of the pyrimidine core to enhance intracellular activity; (ii) introduction of an aromatic amide moiety to establish a hydrogen bond with the kinase hinge region that stabilises binding; (iii) addition of a meta-positioned methyl group to enhance selectivity towards Abl; and (iv) attachment of an *N*-methylpiperazine fragment via a methylene linker

to the benzamide scaffold, thereby increasing aqueous solubility and bioavailability while reducing the toxicity associated with aromatic amines (Matsumoto and Minami 1975; Zimmermann et al. 2001; Capdeville et al. 2002; Manley et al. 2002; Deininger et al. 2005; Manley and Stiefl 2018).

Crystallographic analysis shows that imatinib binds to the inactive (DFG-out) conformation of the kinase. The imatinib–Bcr-Abl complex is stabilised by several hydrogen bonds (with Met318 (hinge), Thr315 (gatekeeper), Glu286, and Asp381 (DFG)) and many hydrophobic interactions. Protonated *N*-methylpiperazine interacts electrostatically with His361. This binding mode is critically dependent on interactions involving the hinge region and the Thr315 residue (Manley and Stiefl 2018; Manley 2019). Single-point mutations in these regions can reduce affinity and drive acquired resistance during prolonged therapy.

Figure 3. Three-dimensional model of the catalytic domain of Bcr-Abl. Structural regions are colour-coded as described in Fig. 2. Generated using PyMOL (Schrödinger, LLC; educational licence).

Second-generation inhibitors: rational structural modifications

The development of second-generation Bcr-Abl tyrosine kinase inhibitors aims to overcome the limitations of imatinib. The goal is to increase inhibitory potency and broaden the spectrum of activity against imatinib-resistant mutations. There are two approaches in this direction: in one case, the DFG-out binding model is preserved, while increased affinity is achieved; in the other case, a more flexible binding model targets the enzyme's active form. The latter approach broadens the mutation range but reduces selectivity and narrows the therapeutic window.

Nilotinib is a structural analogue of imatinib with increased inhibitory potency (Weisberg et al. 2005, 2006). Replacement of the *N*-methylpiperazine fragment with a phenyl ring bearing trifluoromethyl and imidazole groups results in a more rigid structure and enhanced hydrophobic interactions at the active site. The methylimidazole moiety participates in π - π and polar interactions, and the trifluoromethyl group participates in additional electrostatic interactions (Blay and von Mehren 2011). Nilotinib maintains

hydrogen bonds with Met318 and Thr315, but rotation of the amide group creates two additional hydrogen bonds with Glu286 and Asp381, thereby increasing affinity for the DFG-out conformation (Manley et al. 2005). Nilotinib exhibits more than 20-fold greater inhibitory potency against wild-type Bcr-Abl compared to imatinib. The randomised, multicentre, phase III clinical trial ENESTnd demonstrates the superiority of nilotinib in achieving a major molecular response (MMR) compared with the imatinib-treated control arm (Saglio et al. 2010). At the same time, cardiovascular events have been reported with nilotinib treatment, warranting close clinical monitoring (Li et al. 2022). Nilotinib shares the same binding mode as imatinib, which explains its ineffectiveness against the T315I mutation.

The more compact structure of dasatinib allows it to bind to the DFG-in form of the enzyme (Lombardo et al. 2004; Das et al. 2006). It is active against many clinically significant mutations, including those in the P-loop, A-loop, and α C helix, but remains ineffective against the gatekeeper mutation (O'Hare et al. 2005; Tokarski et al. 2006). The thiazolylaminopyrimidine scaffold of dasatinib mimics the adenine moiety of ATP and forms hydrogen bonds with the hinge region, including Met318. Dasatinib is more than 300-fold more potent than imatinib against wild-type Bcr-Abl, but its multi-kinase activity alters the toxicity profile and contributes to adverse effects. The DASISION phase III trial confirmed dasatinib's superior efficacy compared with imatinib (76% vs 64% MMR at 12 months). Non-haematological adverse effects, such as pleural effusion and pulmonary hypertension, have been reported (Cortes et al. 2016).

Bosutinib is a dual Src/Bcr-Abl inhibitor with a good safety profile and metabolic stability. The methylpiperazine fragment attached to the quinolin scaffold improves oral absorption and bioavailability (Boschelli et al. 2001). Bosutinib has a narrow kinase-inhibition profile and does not target c-KIT or PDGFR, which reduces the risk of myelosuppression (Rensing Rix et al. 2009). This inhibitor interacts with both the active and inactive conformations of Bcr-Abl. Its lack of efficacy against T315I mutant cell lines underscores the critical role of the gatekeeper position as a structural barrier to ATP-competitive inhibitors (Levinson and Boxer 2012). The BFORE clinical trial demonstrated superiority over imatinib (MMR 47.2% vs 36.9% at 12 months). Notably, a higher incidence of gastrointestinal and hepatotoxic adverse effects was observed (alanine aminotransferase (ALT) 19.0% vs 1.5% and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) 9.7% vs 1.9% compared to imatinib) (Cortes et al. 2018a). Second-generation inhibitors overcome a broad spectrum of mutant types and achieve deeper responses, but their greater potency often comes at the cost of reduced selectivity and increased toxicity.

Third-generation inhibitors: ponatinib – overcoming the “gatekeeper” mutation

The design of ponatinib represents the culmination of the rational drug design of Bcr-Abl inhibitors. Ponatinib is the first rationally designed TKI to overcome T315I-mediated resistance. The ethynylene ($C\equiv C$) linker enables the mole-

cule to avoid steric conflict with Ile315 while retaining critical interactions within the ATP-binding pocket. It binds to the DFG-out conformation, exhibiting high inhibitory potency towards wild-type and mutant cell lines. Its broad spectrum of activity against other kinases is associated with an increased risk of severe cardiovascular adverse effects. Therefore, careful patient selection and dose optimisation are essential (O'Hare et al. 2009). The PACE trial in patients with treatment failure on first-line TKIs reported a five-year overall survival of 73% (Cortes et al. 2018b). Ponatinib proves that rational drug design can overcome even the T315I mutation while staying within the ATP-competitive paradigm. However, the high incidence of severe adverse events limits its use as a long-term therapy.

The chemical diversity and structural evolution of ATP-competitive TKIs are summarised in Fig. 4, while their comparative pharmacological and clinical characteristics are presented in Table 1. The evolution of tyrosine kinase inhibitors demonstrates that structure-based drug design leads to therapeutic advances but also exposes conceptual limitations. The broader mutation spectrum and high potency often come at the expense of reduced selectivity and increased toxicity. This reveals the need for novel paradigms for regulating kinase activity that are independent of the ATP-binding pocket.

Mechanisms of resistance to tyrosine kinase inhibitors

TKI treatment imposes selective pressure, resulting in the expansion of resistant clones. Resistance can be classified as primary – present before initiating treatment – or acquired during therapy. Therapeutic failure may be due to structural changes in the target tyrosine kinase or to the activation of bypass adaptive cellular mechanisms caused by prolonged inhibition of Bcr-Abl. The mechanisms of resistance are multi-level and adaptive. They are classified as Bcr-Abl-dependent and Bcr-Abl-independent (Ou et al. 2024).

Bcr-Abl-dependent mechanisms

The most common mechanism involves kinase domain mutations that disrupt inhibitor binding through (i) steric conflict in the P-loop, (ii) loss of crucial hydrogen bonds, or (iii) stabilisation of the active conformation of the kinase, which is less sensitive to inhibition. Various mutations in the structure of Bcr-Abl have been identified, but only a few point mutations localised primarily to the P-loop, gatekeeper position, and A-loop are clinically relevant (Branford et al. 2003; Soverini et al. 2011; Zabriskie et al. 2014; Eide and O'Hare 2015). The gatekeeper T315I mutation is a prime example of structure-mediated resis-

Figure 4. Chemical structures of approved TKIs with ATP-competitive mechanisms of action.

Table 1. Comparative pharmacological and clinical profile of approved tyrosine kinase inhibitors in CML. The table has been adapted and summarised based on published biochemical and clinical data from multiple sources (O'Brien et al. 2003; Lombardo et al. 2004; Weisberg et al. 2005; O'Hare et al. 2009; Saglio et al. 2010; Cortes et al. 2016, 2018a, 2018b).

Parameter	imatinib	nilotinib	dasatinib	bosutinib	ponatinib
Pharmacological aspects					
Generation	First	Second	Second	Second	Third
IC ₅₀ (BCR-ABL1, nM)*	~200–600	20–60	0.5–1	~1–5	0.3–0.5
Binding mode	DFG-out (Type II)	DFG-out (Type II)	DFG-in (Type I)	DFG-in/out	DFG-out (Type II)
Activity vs T315I	No	No	No	No	Yes
Kinase selectivity	Abl, KIT, PDGFR, DDR1	Abl, KIT, PDGFR, DDR1	Abl, Src, KIT, PDGFR	Abl, Src, DDR1	Multi-kinase
Clinical efficacy (first-line, 12 months)					
Major molecular response (MMR)	22–28%	43–44%	~46%	~47%	N/A

*IC₅₀ values are representative ranges from biochemical and cellular assays; values are not directly comparable across compounds due to assay variability.

tance: it significantly reduces the effectiveness of first- and second-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitors without affecting the enzyme's catalytic activity. This illustrates the extreme sensitivity of ATP pocket interactions to structural changes at key residue positions. Compound mutations, in which multiple amino acid substitutions occur within the same allele chain, often result in a synergistic loss of sensitivity (Khorashad et al. 2013).

Bcr-Abl-dependent mechanisms also include increased gene expression through BCR-ABL1 amplification, Philadelphia chromosome duplication, or transcriptional up-regulation. In cells with high Bcr-Abl expression levels, even effective kinase inhibition may leave sufficient residual activity to maintain oncogenic signalling and leukaemic proliferation (Gorre et al. 2001; Modi et al. 2007).

Bcr-Abl-independent mechanisms

Resistance can also arise from the activation of alternative signalling pathways that support the viability and proliferation of stem cells in CML (Hamilton et al. 2012). Among the most well-characterised bypass pathways are Src-family kinases, JAK/STAT, Ras/MAPK, and PI3K/Akt/mTOR signalling cascades. These pathways promote proliferation in response to cytokine signals from the tumour microenvironment (Burchert et al. 2005; Packer et al. 2011).

Src-family kinases and Janus kinase (JAK)/signal transducer and activator of transcription (STAT) signalling

Overexpression of Src-family kinases, such as Lck/Yes-related novel tyrosine kinase (Lyn) and haematopoietic cell kinase (Hck), activates STAT transcription factors and JAK2. STAT3 inhibition combined with TKI therapy has been shown to restore sensitivity in resistant cell lines (Eiring et al. 2015; Alves et al. 2021). Increased activity of the adaptor protein Gab2 (Grb2-associated-binding protein 2) affects both the SRC homology region 2 domain-containing phosphatase-2 (Shp2)/Ras/ERK and PI3K/Akt/mTOR cascades, stimulating growth factor-independent proliferation, positioning Gab2 as a resistance biomarker and potential therapeutic target (Halbach et al. 2013; Wöhrle et al. 2013).

Ras/MAPK pathway

The role of RAF serine/threonine kinase (Raf)/mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase (MEK)/extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) signalling in Bcr-Abl-independent resistance is well established. Paradoxical MAPK/ERK activation has been observed during treatment with nilotinib and imatinib, particularly in cells harbouring the T315I mutation (Packer et al. 2011). Preclinical studies demonstrate that combining TKIs with MEK1/2 inhibitors results in greater suppression of cell proliferation compared to monotherapy (Ma et al. 2014).

PI3K/Akt/mTOR pathway: This pathway plays a crucial role in maintaining cell survival and proliferation (Burchert et al. 2005). A combination of nilotinib with the dual PI3K/mTOR inhibitor NVP-BEZ235 has shown efficacy against T315I-mutant and ponatinib-resistant cell lines. Akt also activates nuclear factor kappa B (NF-κB), further promoting cell survival (Okabe et al. 2014; Patel et al. 2017; He et al. 2021). These findings support the rationale for combination therapeutic strategies targeting multiple pathways simultaneously.

Membrane transporter variability

Pharmacokinetic factors, especially variability in membrane transporter activity, are another important Bcr-Abl-independent resistance mechanism. The organic cation transporter 1 (OCT1) mediates imatinib uptake, and low OCT1 activity correlates with poor therapeutic response (White et al. 2010). In contrast, the uptake of nilotinib and dasatinib is OCT1-independent, explaining their efficacy in OCT1-deficient patients (Giannoudis et al. 2008). Increased expression of efflux transporters P-glycoprotein (P-gp/ABCB1) and breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP/ABCG2) accelerates TKI export and reduces intracellular drug concentrations. All approved Bcr-Abl inhibitors are P-gp substrates, and high ABCB1 expression correlates with poorer prognosis, although higher TKI doses can partially overcome this effect (Ammar et al. 2020).

Genomic instability and epigenetic alterations

Overexpression of the fusion BCR-ABL1 gene leads to the accumulation of additional chromosomal and molecular abnormalities, inducing genomic instability and clonal evolution (Kim et al. 2010). Epigenetic modifications, including DNA hypermethylation and histone acetylation/phosphorylation, remodel chromatin structure and alter gene expression. Mutations in epigenetic regulators have been reported in cases of resistance (Rinke et al. 2020). Individual TKI pharmacokinetic variations – influenced by cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP3A4)-mediated metabolism, drug–drug interactions, and plasma protein binding – further contribute to treatment response heterogeneity (Sun et al. 2024).

CML resistance arises through both target-site alterations, such as kinase domain mutations that prevent inhibitor binding, and biological adaptation through bypass signalling, leukaemic stem cell persistence, and pharmacokinetic variability. Understanding these processes enables treatment optimisation and development of alternative strategies, including allosteric inhibitors and combination approaches.

Prospects and future directions in CML therapy

Allosteric inhibitors

Asciminib (ABL001) is the first representative of a new class of allosteric inhibitors that bind to the myristoyl pocket in the C-lobe of Bcr-Abl, rather than to the ATP-binding site. This mechanism of action induces autoinhibition of the kinase, in which the N-terminal structure blocks the catalytic domain, regardless of the DFG motif's conformation (Schoepfer et al. 2018). Asciminib received FDA approval in 2021 for Ph+ CML in the chronic or accelerated phase in patients with ≥ 2 prior TKIs or with a T315I mutation (U.S. Food and Drug Administration 2021). In the randomised phase III ASCEMBL study in patients treated with TKIs, a major molecular response at week 24 was observed in 25.5% of patients treated with asciminib versus 13.2% with bosutinib therapy (Réa et al. 2021). The allosteric mechanism of action allows for combination with ATP-competitive TKIs to achieve a synergistic effect. Preclinical data demonstrate that the combination of asciminib with nilotinib or ponatinib eliminates resistant clones harbouring complex mutations that are insensitive to monotherapy (Eide et al. 2019). Despite asciminib's clinical efficacy, resistance has already emerged through mutations in the myristoyl binding pocket (Breccia 2024; Batar et al. 2025). This demonstrates that allosteric inhibition, while mechanistically distinct from ATP-competitive approaches, faces evolutionary pressure and does not eliminate the problem of resistance.

Combined therapeutic strategies

Redundant survival pathways make combinations an attractive strategy. Combinations targeting downstream signalling pathways aim to suppress compensatory proliferative

pathways. The combination of dasatinib and trametinib (MEK1/2 inhibitor) has been reported in individual cases of Philadelphia chromosome-positive (Ph+) acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (ALL) and other neoplasms (Hollis et al. 2024). Dasatinib enhances the antitumour activity of trametinib *in vitro* and *in vivo* against Kirsten rat sarcoma viral oncogene homolog (KRAS)-mutant cancer models (Rao et al. 2018). The combination of imatinib and everolimus (mTOR inhibitor) demonstrates synergism *in vitro*. Everolimus reduces the viability of both imatinib-sensitive and imatinib-resistant cell lines by inducing apoptosis and cell cycle arrest (Alves et al. 2019). PI3K/mTOR inhibition sensitises CML cells to nilotinib (Carayol et al. 2010; Airiau et al. 2013).

Apoptosis-focused strategies such as BCL-2 inhibition aim to restore intrinsic cell death programmes in leukaemic stem cells. Venetoclax (BCL-2 inhibitor) targets leukaemic stem cells unresponsive to TKI monotherapy by inhibiting the anti-apoptotic protein BCL-2, which is overexpressed in CML cells (Cao et al. 2023). Combined inhibition of Bcr-Abl and BCL-2 leads to changes in the lipid metabolism of leukaemic stem cells, inducing compensatory activation of lysosomal acid lipase A (LIPA) and increased production of free fatty acids, which provide an alternative energy source and serve as a mechanism for adaptive resistance to therapy (Minhajuddin et al. 2024). Despite a strong mechanistic rationale, most evidence for combination therapy comes from preclinical models or case reports, with limited prospective clinical trial data.

Innovative strategies: PROTACs, immunotherapy, and personalised therapy

PROTACs (Proteolysis-Targeting Chimeras) are bifunctional molecules that induce proteasomal degradation of Bcr-Abl instead of inhibiting kinase activity. In preclinical studies, the lead compound GMB-475 has been shown to induce rapid, concentration-dependent degradation of Bcr-Abl (half-maximal degradation concentration, $DC_{50} \approx 340$ nM in K562) and to show activity against selected resistant mutations (Burslem et al. 2019). PROTAC-based approaches targeting Bcr-Abl remain largely preclinical, with no clinically validated degraders reported to date.

Immunotherapy strategies, including CD70-targeting chimeric antigen receptor T-cell (CAR-T) cells and CD33 \times CD3 bispecific antibodies, have demonstrated activity in early clinical trials in patients with acute myeloid leukaemia (AML), but their applicability in the chronic phase of CML remains unclear (Wu et al. 2023).

The integration of next-generation sequencing (NGS)-based mutation profiling and therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM) optimises therapeutic outcomes in CML. NGS allows detection of mutations at $\geq 1\%$ frequency (versus $\geq 10\text{--}20\%$ with Sanger), which is important for early identification of resistant clones (Machova Polakova et al. 2015; Soverini et al. 2016). There are specific issues with this method – PCR-mediated recombination can create false complex variants, as hybrid DNA products arising during amplification can be misinterpreted as real mutations. This leads to an overestimation of the frequency of some

mutation variants, especially when PCR amplicons are used (Soverini et al. 2020). TDM-based dose adjustment at suboptimal imatinib plasma levels (<1000 ng/mL) improves molecular response (Gotta et al. 2014; Soverini et al. 2020). The combination of mutation analysis and pharmacokinetic monitoring enables therapy customisation and timely adaptation in the event of a suboptimal response.

Conclusion

Tyrosine kinase inhibitors have transformed chronic myeloid leukaemia from a rapidly fatal disease into a manageable chronic condition. Since the introduction of imatinib, annual mortality has declined from approximately 10–20% to approximately 1–2%, resulting in markedly improved long-term survival and a steadily increasing prevalence of CML (Jabbour and Kantarjian 2024). However, acquired resistance – particularly the T315I mutation – limits long-term therapeutic success in 20–30% of patients (Nicolini et al. 2013).

CML therapy is approaching the limits of single-target inhibition. Sustained disease control increasingly depends on rational combination therapy and treatment individualisation rather than inhibitor potency alone (Kantarjian et al. 2025). Current strategies to overcome resistance include three main approaches: allosteric inhibitors such as asciminib, combination regimens with non-competitive mechanisms, and personalised treatment based on mutational profiling and pharmacokinetic monitoring. The parallel development of allosteric inhibitors and PROTAC technologies expands therapeutic options beyond classical single-target ATP-pocket inhibition. CML remains a paradigm for structure-based drug design and targeted therapy. The evolution from imatinib to modern multimodal approaches illustrates how rational pharmacology has been shaped by clinical constraints and resistance.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

The following AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript):

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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